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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A METHOD FOR THE
SIMULTANEOUS ASSESSMENT OF AZITHROMYCIN AND
LEVOFLOXACIN BY RP-HPLC IN TABLET DOSAGE FORM****Ravindar Bairam., A. Shirisha, P. Balakrishanaiah, and Manjunath S.Y**Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vill: Velikatta, Mdl: Kondapak, Dist: Siddipet,
Telangana. PIN:502277.**Abstract:****Objective:** A New method was established for simultaneous estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin by RP-HPLC method.**Methods:** Chromatographic separations were carried using HPLC equipped with Auto Sampler and PDA Detector, Agilent ZorbaxC18, 250x4.6, 5 μ column with a mobile phase composition of K₂HPO₄: Methanol (40:60) have been delivered at a flow rate of 1ml/min and the detection was carried out using waters HPLC auto sampler, separation module 2695 HPLC system with PDA detector at wavelength 265 nm.**Results:** The retention time for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin were 3.0154 and 3.436 minute respectively. The correlation coefficient values in linearity were found to be 0.999 and concentration range 50-150 μ g/ml for Levofloxacin and 50-150 μ g/ml for Azithromycin respectively. For accuracy The total recovery was found to be 97 % and 103 % for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin. LOD and LOQ for Levofloxacin 2.830 and 943 μ g/mL, LOD and LOQ for Azithromycin 2.94 and 9.80 μ g/mL. All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.**Conclusion:** The results of study showed that the proposed RP-HPLC method is a simple, accurate, precise, rugged, robust, fast and reproducible, which may be useful for the routine estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in pharmaceutical dosage form.**Keywords:** Levofloxacin, Azithromycin, RP-HPLC, Simultaneous estimation.**Corresponding author:****Ravindar Bairam,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Levofloxacin is a fluoroquinolone antibiotic used to treat infections caused by susceptible bacteria of the upper respiratory tract, skin and skin structures, urinary tract, and prostate, as well as for post-exposure treatment of inhaled anthrax and the plague. Levofloxacin, like other fluoroquinolone antibiotics, exerts its antimicrobial activity via the inhibition of two key bacterial enzymes: DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV. Both targets are type II topoisomerases, but have unique functions within the bacterial cell. DNA gyrase is an enzyme found only in bacteria that introduces negative supercoils into DNA during replication - this helps to relieve torsional strain caused by the introduction of positive supercoils during replication, and this negative supercoils are essential for chromosome condensation and the promotion of transcription initiation. It is comprised of four subunits (two A subunits and two B subunits) of which the A subunits appear to be the target of fluoroquinolone antibiotics. Bacterial topoisomerase IV, in addition to contributing to the relaxation of positive supercoils, is essential at the terminal stages of DNA replication and functions to "unlink" newly replicated chromosomes to allow for the completion of cell division.¹⁻⁴ IUPAC name of Levofloxacin is (2S)-7-fluoro-2-methyl-6-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-10-oxo-4-oxa-1-azatricyclo[7.3.1.0[^]{5,13}]trideca-5(13),6,8,11-

Figure 1: Structure of Levofloxacin
Figure 2: Structure of Azithromycin

Literature survey revealed few analytical techniques for the estimation of azithromycin⁹⁻¹⁰ and levofloxacin¹¹⁻¹⁶ individually or in combination with other drugs but limited number of methods are available for the determination of these drugs in combination. So the aim of the present study is to

tetraene-11-carboxylic acid. Molecular Formula is C₁₈H₂₀FN₃O₄. Molecular Weight is 361.3.

Azithromycin is a broad-spectrum macrolide antibiotic with a long half-life and a high degree of tissue penetration. It was initially approved by the FDA in 1991. It is primarily used for the treatment of respiratory, enteric and genitourinary infections and may be used instead of other macrolides for some sexually transmitted and enteric infections. It is structurally related to erythromycin. In order to replicate, bacteria require a specific process of protein synthesis, enabled by ribosomal proteins. Azithromycin binds to the 23S rRNA of the bacterial 50S ribosomal subunit. It stops bacterial protein synthesis by inhibiting the transpeptidation/translocation step of protein synthesis and by inhibiting the assembly of the 50S ribosomal subunit. This results in the control of various bacterial infections, Label. The strong affinity of macrolides, including azithromycin, for bacterial ribosomes, is consistent with their broad-spectrum antibacterial activities.⁵⁻⁸ IUPAC name of 4-(dimethylamino)-3-hydroxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy}-2-ethyl-3,4,10-trihydroxy-13-[(2R,4R,5S,6S)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-4,6-dimethyloxan-2-yl]oxy}-3,5,6,8,10,12,14-heptamethyl-1-oxa-6-azacyclopentadecan-15-one. Molecular formula is C₃₈H₇₂N₂O₁₂. Molecular Weight is 748.9.

develop a simple and specific RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of these two drugs in bulk and dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents: Levofloxacin and Azithromycin were Purchased from Hetero drugs. NaH₂PO₄ was analytical grade supplied by Finerchem limited, Orthophosphoric acid (Merck),

and Water and Methanol for HPLC (Lichrosolv (Merck).

Equipment and Chromatographic Conditions:

The chromatography was performed on a Waters 2695 HPLC system, equipped with an auto sampler, UV detector and Empower 2 software. Analysis was carried out at 265 nm with column Agilent ZorbaxC18, 250x4.6, 5 μ , dimensions at 30°C temperature. The optimized mobile phase consists of K₂HPO₄: Methanol (400:600). Flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min.

Preparation of solutions:**PREPARATION OF MOBILE PHASE:**

Transfer 500ml of HPLC water into 500ml of beaker and DiPotassium hydrogen phosphate adjust pH 3.5 using O-phosphoric acid. Transfer the above solution 400ml of K₂HPO₄, 600ml of Methanol is used as mobile phase. They are mixed and sonicated for 20min.

PREPARATION OF STANDARD SOLUTION:

Accurately weigh and transfer 100mg of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin into 100ml of volumetric flask and add 10ml of Methanol and sonicate 10min (or) shake 5min and make with water. Transfers the above solution into 5ml into 50ml volumetric flask dilute to volume with water.

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE STOCK SOLUTION:

Commercially available 20 tablets were weighed and powdered the powdered equivalent to the 500mg of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin of active ingredients were transfer into a 100ml of volumetric flask and add 10ml of Methanol and sonicate 20min (or) shake 10min and makeup with water. Transfers above solution 5ml into 50ml of the volumetric flask dilute the volume with Methanol. And the solution was filtered through 0.45 μ m filter before injecting into HPLC system.

Sample preparation:

10 tablets were weighed and crushed, from the powdered tablets, weighed accurately about 500mg (500mg Levofloxacin and 500mg Azithromycin) into a 100 ml volumetric flask and 50 ml of mobile phase was added. The mixture was subjected to sonication for 20 min with intermediate

shaking for complete extraction of drugs. Filtered and cooled to room temperature and solution was made up to mark with mobile phase. From the above solution 5 mL is taken and further diluted in 25 ml volumetric flasks with mobile phase. To acquire a concentration of 500mg Levofloxacin and 500mg Azithromycin.

Standard preparation:

Accurately weighed quantity of 500mg Levofloxacin and 500mg Azithromycin was taken in a 100 ml volumetric flask and 50 ml of mobile phase was added. The mixture was subjected to sonication for 20 min with intermediate shaking for complete extraction of drugs. Filtered and cooled to room temperature and solution was made up to mark with mobile phase. From the above solution 5 ml is taken and further diluted in 25 mL volumetric flasks with mobile phase. To acquire a concentration of 500mg Levofloxacin and 500mg Azithromycin.

Procedure:

Separately injected both the standard (2 injections) and sample preparations (2 injections) into the chromatographic system and recorded the peak area responses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**METHOD:**

The developed chromatographic method was validated for system suitability, linearity accuracy, precision, ruggedness and robustness as per ICH guidelines.

System suitability parameters: To evaluate system suitability parameters such as retention time, tailing factor and USP theoretical plate count, the mobile phase was allowed to flow through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min to equilibrate the column at ambient temperature. Analysis was carried out at 265 nm with column Agilent ZorbaxC18, 250x4.6, 5 μ , dimensions at 30°C temperature. The optimized mobile phase consists of K₂HPO₄: Methanol (400:600). Flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min.

Retention time, tailing factor and USP theoretical plate count of the developed method are shown in table 1.

Table 1: System suitability parameters

parameter	Levofloxacin	Azithromycin	Acceptance criteria
Retention time	3.154	3.436	+10
Theoretical plates	14206	11075	>2500
Tailing factor	1.35	1.55	<2.00
% RSD	0.3	0.2	<2.00

Assay of pharmaceutical formulation: The proposed validated method was successfully applied to determine Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in their tablet dosage form. The result obtained for was comparable with the corresponding labeled amounts and they were shown in Table-2.

Table 2: Assay results for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

S.No	Levofloxacin		Azithromycin	
	Standard Area	Sample area	Standard Area	Sample area
1	1130289	1131289	1112555	1111555
2	1135307	1133307	1116367	1112367
3	1136018	1134018	1113656	1110656
4	1131067	1131067	1113585	1113585
5	1130362	1129362	1114698	1114698
Average	113268.6	113172.4	111417.2	1112572
Tablet average weight	1383.0		1383.0	
Standard weight	500		500	
Sample weight	1383.0		1383.0	
Label amount	500		500	
std.purity	99.1		99.7	
%Assay	99.31		99.40	

Figure 3: Standard chromatogram

Figure 4: Sample chromatogram

Figure 5: Blank chromatogram

Validation of Analytical method:

Linearity: The linearity study was performed for the concentration of 50 ppm to 150 ppm. Each level was injected into chromatographic system. The area of each level was used for calculation of correlation coefficient. Inject each level into the chromatographic system and measure the peak area. Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient. The results are shown in table 3,4.

Table 3: Linearity results of Levofloxacin

s.no	Conc($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	RT	Area
1.	50	3.155	568388
2.	75	3.146	852253
3.	100	3.136	1131849
4.	125	3.139	1427500
5.	150	3.137	1700737
Std.dev			
Slope			
Intercept			
Correlation coefficient (r^2)			0.999

Figure 6: Linearity graph for Levofloxacin

Table 4: Linearity results of Azithromycin

s.no	Conc($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	RT	Area
1.	50	3.443	556498
2.	75	3.433	834448
3.	100	3.426	1113804
4.	125	3.431	1395652
5.	150	3.428	1660930
Std.dev			
Slope			
Intercept			
Correlation coefficient (r^2)			0.999

Figure 6: Linearity graph for Azithromycin

Accuracy studies: The accuracy was determined by help of recovery study. The recovery method carried out at three level 50%, 100%, 150% and 50%, 100%, 150% Inject the standard solutions into chromatographic system. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values. The results are shown in table 5,6.

Table 5: Showing accuracy results for Levofloxacin

S.NO	Accuracy level	Sample name	Sample weight	$\mu\text{g/ml}$ added	$\mu\text{g/ml}$ found	% Recovery	% Mean
1	50%	1	691.50	49.500	49.53	100	100
		2	691.50	49.500	49.58	100	
		3	691.50	49.500	49.57	100	
		4	691.50	49.500	49.53	100	
		5	691.50	49.500	49.55	100	
		6	691.50	49.500	49.53	100	
2	100%	1	1383.0	99.000	98.65	100	100
		2	1383.0	99.000	98.49	99	
		3	1383.0	99.000	98.50	99	
3	150%	1	2074.50	148.500	148.82	100	100
		2	2074.50	148.500	148.25	100	
		3	2074.50	148.500	148.84	100	
		4	2074.50	148.500	148.20	100	
		5	2074.50	148.500	148.94	100	
		6	2074.50	148.500	148.37	100	

Table 6: Showing accuracy results for Azithromycin

S.NO	Accuracy level	Sample name	Sample weight	$\mu\text{g/ml}$ added	$\mu\text{g/ml}$ found	% Recovery	% Mean
1	50%	1	691.50	50.000	49.85	100	100
		2	691.50	50.000	49.82	100	
		3	691.50	50.000	49.88	100	
		4	691.50	50.000	49.87	100	
		5	691.50	50.000	49.88	100	
		6	691.50	50.000	49.84	100	
		1	1383.00	100.000	99.93	100	100
		2	1383.00	100.000	99.86	100	

2	100%	3	1383.00	100.000	99.75	100	
3	150%	1	2074.50	150.000	148.87	99	100
		2	2074.50	150.000	148.99	99	
		3	2074.50	150.000	149.17	99	
		4	2074.50	150.000	148.76	99	
		5	2074.50	150.000	149.56	100	
		6	2074.50	150.000	148.87	99	

Precision Studies: precision was calculated from Coefficient of variance for six replicate injections of the standard. The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six Injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found. The results are shown in table 7,8.

Table 7: Precision results for Levofloxacin

S.no	RT	Area	%Assay
injection1	3.144	1130289	98
injection2	3.141	1135307	99
injection3	3.142	1136018	99
injection4	3.145	1131067	99
injection5	3.142	1130362	99
injection6	3.138	1133569	99
Mean			99
Std. Dev.			0.22
% RSD			0.22

Table 8: Precision results for Azithromycin

S.no	RT	Area	%Assay
injection1	3.431	1112555	100
injection 2	3.429	1116367	100
injection 3	3.428	1113656	100
injection 4	3.432	1113585	100
injection 5	3.430	1114698	100
injection 6	3.428	1114883	100
Mean			100
Std. Dev.			0.12
%RSD			0.12

Robustness: As part of the Robustness, deliberate change in the Flow rate, Mobile Phase composition, Temperature Variation was made to evaluate the impact on the method. The flow rate was varied at 0.8 ml/min to 1.2 ml/min. The results are shown in table 9,10.

Table 9 : Robustness data for Levofloxacin

parameter	RT	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry
Decreased flow rate(0.8ml/min)	4.178	12562	1.52
Actual flow rate(1.0ml/min)	3.154	11143	1.49
Increased flow rate(1.2ml/min)	2.516	10342	1.40
Decreased temperature(20 ⁰ c)	4.179	12660	1.52
Actual temperature(25 ⁰ c)	3.154	11143	1.49
Increased temperature(30 ⁰ c)	4.183	12750	1.52

Table 10: Robustness data for Azithromycin

parameter	RT	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry
Decreased flow rate (0.8ml/min)	4.564	14378	1.30
Actual flow rate (1.0ml/min)	3.439	13998	1.30
Increased flow rate (1.2ml/min)	2.746	12574	1.32
Decreased temperature(20 ⁰ c)	4.564	14785	1.28
Actual temperature(25 ⁰ c)	3.439	13998	1.30
Increasedtemperature(30 ⁰ c)	4.568	14978	1.30

LOD and LOQ: The sensitivity of RP-HPLC was determined from LOD and LOQ. Which were calculated from the calibration curve using the following equations as per ICH guidelines. The results are shown in table 11,12.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma/S \text{ and}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma/S, \text{ where}$$

σ = Standard deviation of y intercept of regression line,

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Table 11: LOD of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

s.no	Sample name	RT	Area
1	Levofloxacin	3.146	1411711
2	Azithromycin	3.433	2061485

Table 12: LOQ data for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

S.no	Sample name	RT	Area
1	Levofloxacin	3.142	1380760
2	Azithromycin	3.430	1866930

CONCLUSION:

The validated HPLC method developed for the quantitative quality control determination of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in combination was evaluated for system suitability, specificity, sensitivity, linearity, range, accuracy (recovery), precision (repeatability and intermediate precision), and robustness. All the validation results were within the allowed specifications of ICH guidelines. The developed method has proven to be rapid, accurate, and stability-indicating for the simultaneous determination of combined Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in tablet dosage form in the presence of excipients and the degradation products. There was always a complete separation of both ingredients from their degradation products and from the placebo. As a result, the proposed HPLC method could be adopted for the quantitative quality control and routine analysis of the tablet dosage form.

REFERENCES:

1. Fish DN, Chow AT: The clinical pharmacokinetics of levofloxacin. Clin Pharmacokinet. 1997 Feb;32(2):101-19. doi: 10.2165/00003088-199732020-00002.
2. Giri P, Naidu S, Patel N, Patel H, Srinivas NR: Evaluation of In Vitro Cytochrome P450 Inhibition and In Vitro Fate of Structurally Diverse N-Oxide Metabolites: Case Studies with Clozapine, Levofloxacin, Roflumilast, Voriconazole and Zopiclone. Eur J Drug Metab Pharmacokinet. 2017 Aug;42(4):677-688. doi: 10.1007/s13318-016-0385-7.
3. Sato T, Mishima E, Mano N, Abe T, Yamaguchi H: Potential Drug Interactions Mediated by Renal Organic Anion Transporter OATP4C1. J Pharmacol Exp Ther. 2017 Aug;362(2):271-277. doi: 10.1124/jpet.117.241703. Epub 2017 May 26.

4. Parvez MM, Kaisar N, Shin HJ, Jung JA, Shin JG: Inhibitory Interaction Potential of 22 Antituberculosis Drugs on Organic Anion and Cation Transporters of the SLC22A Family. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 2016 Oct 21;60(11):6558-6567. doi: 10.1128/AAC.01151-16. Print 2016 Nov.
5. Peters DH, Friedel HA, McTavish D: Azithromycin. A review of its antimicrobial activity, pharmacokinetic properties and clinical efficacy. *Drugs.* 1992 Nov;44(5):750-99. doi: 10.2165/00003495-199244050-00007. [Article]
6. McMullan BJ, Mostaghim M: Prescribing azithromycin. *Aust Prescr.* 2015 Jun;38(3):87-9. Epub 2015 Jun 1. [Article]
7. Fohner AE, Sparreboom A, Altman RB, Klein TE: PharmGKB summary: Macrolide antibiotic pathway, pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics. *Pharmacogenet Genomics.* 2017 Apr;27(4):164-167. doi: 10.1097/FPC.0000000000000270. [Article]
8. Champney WS, Miller M: Inhibition of 50S ribosomal subunit assembly in *Haemophilus influenzae* cells by azithromycin and erythromycin. *Curr Microbiol.* 2002 Jun;44(6):418-24.
9. Irin Dewan, Tasnuva Amin, Faisal Hossain Md, MoynulHasan, Sayeeda Fahmee Chowdhury, Mahjabeen Gazi and Ashraful Islam Dewan SM. Development and validation of a new HPLC method for the estimation of azithromycin in bulk. *IJPSR.* 2013;4(1):282-286.
10. Narendra Nyola and Govinda Samy Jeyabalan. Simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Cefixime in A Pharmaceutical Ingredients Spectrophotometry. *J DMed.* 2012;4(2):27-32.
11. Manish kumar, Gurralla srikanth, Venkateshwar rao and Sambasivarao KRS. Development and validation of HPLC UV method for the estimation of levofloxacin in human plasma.
12. Shafrose Syed and Haritha Pavan. Validated Simultaneous Estimation and Development of Levofloxacin and Ornidazole by RP-HPLC Method. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2012;4(4):52-55.
13. Kole Spandana, Rathnakar CH and Kole Bhavana. Method Development and Validation for the Simultaneous Estimation of Levofloxacin and Cefpodoxime Proxetil by Using RPHPLC in Combined Tablet Dosage. *J Chromatogr Sci.* 2007;45(8):531-6.
14. Chepurwar SB, Shirkhedkar AA, Bari SB, Fursule RA and Surana S. Validated HPTLC method for simultaneous estimation of levofloxacin hemihydrates and ornidazole in pharmaceutical dosage form. *J Chromatogr Sci.* 2007;45(8):531-6.
15. Batuk Dabhi, Bhavesh Parmar, Nithish Patel, Yashwanth sinhJadeja, Madhavi Patel, Hetal Jebaliya, Danish Karala and Shah AK. Stability indicating UPLC method for the determination of levofloxacin hemihydrate in Pharmaceutical dosage form. *Chromatography Research International.* 2013;432753.
16. Ceema Mathew, Suman B, Ajitha M and Sathesh Babu PR. A green analytical method for the simultaneous estimation of levofloxacin and ambroxyl hydrochloride using hydrotrophy and first derivative UV spectroscopy. *Orient J Chem.* 2014;30(3):4971-6.